

A First Assessment of the Conservation of the Mummified Human Remains in the Museo Egizio in Turin in the Framework of the "Mummy Conservation Project"

Marco Samadelli, Giulia Gregori, Frank Maixner, Marco Rossani, Paolo Del Vesco, Matilde Borla, Alice Paladin, Christina Wurst, Katja Sterflinger-Gleixner, Christian Voitl, Marta Cibin, Gregory S. Thomas, Bruno Frohlich, Randall C. Thompson, Albert R. Zink

The Museo Egizio in Turin holds a unique collection of 116 mummified or skeletal human bodies or body parts. This collection is currently under study by the "Mummy Conservation Project", a collaborative venture of the Museo Egizio, the Institute for Mummy Studies of Eurac Research, the Soprintendenza Archeologia del Piemonte, and the Horus Group, whose aim is to improve mummy conservation techniques. In the context of this project, an assessment of the state of preservation of the mummified human remains was carried out by monitoring basic physical parameters (temperature, relative humidity and water activity) and by performing a fungal survey. The latter revealed the presence on the mummified material of fungal spores and mycelia that could possibly pose a biodegradative threat. However, all the current physical parameters show that the mummies are stored under optimal environmental conditions, which will suppress any microbial up-growth.

ملخص البحث:

يحتوي المتحف المصري في تورينو على مجموعة فريدة تضم 116 قطعة ما بين موميوات بشرية محنطة أو هياكل عظمية أو أجزاء بشرية محنطة. حالياً هذه المجموعة قيد الدراسة من قبل "مشروع الحفاظ على الموميوات"، هو مشروع تعاوني ما بين المتحف المصري ومعهد دراسات المومياء لأبحاث يوراك ومكتب الحفاظ على التراث الأثري في مقاطعة بيمونتي ومجموعة حورس، التي تهدف إلى تحسين تقنيات الحفاظ على الموميوات. في نطاق هذا المشروع، تم تقييم حالة الحفظ للبقايا البشرية المحنطة من خلال مراقبة العوامل الفيزيائية الأساسية (درجة الحرارة والرطوبة النسبية ونشاط الجزيئات المائية) وإجراء مسح للفطور. كشفت هذه الأخيرة عن وجود فطور وبكتريات فطرية على المواد المحنطة والتي يمكن أن تشكل تهديداً بالتحلل الحيوي. ومع ذلك تظهر جميع المقاييس الفيزيائية الحالية أن الموميوات يتم تخزينها في ظل ظروف بيئية مثالية، والتي سوف تثبط أي نمو للميكروبات.

1. Introduction

The first set of Egyptian mummies arrived in Turin following the scientific/commercial expedition undertaken by the traveler and naturalist, Vitaliano Donati, a professor of botany at the University of Turin, at the behest of King Charles Emmanuel III of Savoy between 1759 and 1762. In Egypt, Dona-

ti collected some 1,689 scientific samples and objects,¹ including eighteen animal mummies. A second group of mummies, many probably coming from the ancient Egyptian capital city of Thebes (modern-day Luxor in southern Egypt), was collected by Bernardino Drovetti, Consul General of France to Egypt, and was bought, for the Turin collection,

by the Savoy king Charles Felix in 1824.² In 1888, when the two-volume catalogue of the Museo Egizio was completed by Ariodante Fabretti (1816-1894), Francesco Rossi (1827-1912) and Rodolfo Vittorio Lanzone (1834-1907), it included a total of twelve complete human mummies, nine heads – two of which were associated with a hand – two hands with rings, four pseudo-mummies, and seventy-eight animal mummies. The human mummies entered the collection inside wooden anthropoid coffins, and the inscriptions that grace these coffins specify the names and professions of the deceased they were meant for, supposedly the same people whose mummified bodies were contained in the coffins.³ Finally, thanks to Ernesto Schiaparelli, director of the Museo Egizio between 1894 and 1928, the number of mummies in the collection was further increased. A buying trip to Egypt, done by Schiaparelli in 1900/1901, led to the purchase of more than 1,500 items, including two naturally mummified adult bodies and the mummy of a small child dating to about 3500 BCE. But it is especially since the foundation of the Italian Archaeological Mission to Egypt in 1903 that a large number of human remains was discovered at various sites along the Nile, during many excavation seasons directed by Egyptologists Ernesto Schiaparelli and, later on, Giulio Farina, who were assisted, since 1914, by anthropologist Giovanni Marro.⁴ A total of 116 mummified or skeletal human bodies and body parts are recorded today in the Museum database as coming from these fieldwork campaigns, but 20 more mummies, 650 complete skeletons, and 144 skulls, presently held in the Turin Museum of Anthropology and Ethnography,⁵ most likely also derive from the same excavations.

Given the increasing attention among researchers to the mummified human remains held in the Museo Egizio in Turin, in 2016 the “Mummy Conservation Project” was set up, with the aim of incorporating the data and knowledge acquired so far on these human remains in order to develop a protocol for proper museum conservation and display.

The goals of the “Mummy Conservation Project” illustrated in this paper were the following:

- Taking thermo-hygrometric measurements in the galleries, the inside of display cases, in the mum-

my storage room, and in the room where the research operations were carried out.

- Measuring the water activity (aw) of the mummies.
- Fungal spore sampling of the air in the galleries, inside a display case, in the mummy storage room, and in the room where the research operations were carried out.
- Fungal survey of the mummified material.

2. Research aim

In view of the Museo Egizio and Eurac Research’s common interest in developing know-how to help preserve all the Museo Egizio’s mummies – both those on display and those in storage – special emphasis was placed on testing water activity (aw), a parameter that affects the rate of biochemical decay in organic tissues. This important parameter is significantly affected by temperature and relative humidity in the conservation environment. In parallel to the assessment of this physical parameter, a first microbial survey was performed.

To identify the presence of possible superficial growing fungi, samples of both textiles and skin were taken using non-invasive contact plates.

To obtain further knowledge of the environmental conditions the mummies are presently experiencing, the researchers also took samples of spores present in the air inside the storage room where the mummies were kept, in a display case in the permanent galleries, and in the room where the research operations were carried out.

The aim of this work is to expand on research on the conservation organic objects of historical and artistic interest by assessing both biological and physical-chemical conservation requirements.

3. Material and methods

3.1 Thermo-hygrometric measurement of the exhibition areas, inside a display case, in the mummy storage room, and in the room where the research operations were carried out

Thanks to historical data relative to the thermo-hygrometric conditions of the museum’s exhibition spaces and the storage space where the mummies were kept (prior to the inauguration of the new galleries in 2015), it was possible to identify the sea-

Fig. 1: A phase of a non-invasive water activity (aw) test carried out on the mummy of Kha (Suppl. 8431). Picture by Eurac Research, Institute for Mummy Studies.

sonal trend these relics were subjected to.

With the exception of the room where the Tomb of Kha and Merit was display – where a wall-mounted air conditioner and a portable humidifier were installed – all the rest of the museum and storage lacked an air conditioning system. Climate monitoring took place in “sample” mode over different periods and in different areas of the museum with the aid of data loggers (HumiStick). The recorded temperature ranged between 21 °C and 30 °C, and the recorded relative humidity between 30 % and 66 %. In 2015, a new air conditioning system was installed, serving all the exhibition halls, the Foundation’s offices, and the storage spaces. It is powered by an underground thermo-cooling plant using geothermal energy.

To date, the museum’s different exhibition areas have depended on auxiliary machines whose temperature and relative humidity values can be individually and independently set.

3.2 Measuring water activity (aw) of the mummies

As regards this specific phase of the project, a total of 106 organic samples were analysed, both of a vegetal nature (bandage linen) and of human origin

(fragments of bone, skin, muscles, connective tissue, hair, Fig. 1).

To measure the water activity (aw) value, the Rotronic instrument, model HygroPalm HP-23-AW-A, was used. Prior to measuring the samples, the HC2-AW and the relative Rotronic HC2-SH measurement probe were calibrated as needed.

Immediately after sampling the mummified organic tissues, the water activity of the samples was examined. The samples were then placed inside special sample holders, previously sterilised. The Rotronic HW4 software version 3.8.0 was used to validate the measurements obtained. Once the PC was connected to the analyser, it was possible, through this application, to set the necessary operating settings in order to obtain the measurement (Fig. 2).

Simultaneously with the water activity (aw) acquisition phase, the temperature and relative humidity values of the environment were obtained. The time required to acquire each sample is approximately 5 minutes. At the end of each acquisition, a validation certificate was produced in form of a PDF file.

3.3 Sampling and cultivation of fungi

Non-invasive sampling using contact agar plates (DG18 and 2 % MEA, Merck) was performed as pre-

Fig. 2: Instrumental configuration for assessing water activity (aw). Picture by Marco Samadelli/Eurac Research, Institute for Mummy Studies.

viously described⁶ on different materials for the cultivation of superficial growing fungi (Fig. 3). The samples were taken from different materials found in the mummies, including soft tissue and textile material. We generated data from 18 mummies from the museum's storage room "Ipogeo magazzino visitabile" and 6 mummies stored in display cases. Air-borne fungi were collected on DG18 and 2 % MEA plates using an air sampler (SAS) Super-90 (PBI International, Milan, Italy), with a sampling volume of 100 litres (Fig. 4). Fungi collected from the contact plates and air samples were purified by several transfers onto 2 % MEA and DG18 plates.

3.3.1 DNA extraction, PCR amplification and sequence analysis

Pure cultures were identified based on the sequencing of internal transcribed spacer region (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2), a sequence that can be used as a phylogenetic marker. DNA was extracted from the purified cultures using fresh mycelia, as described by Michaelsen et al.⁷ For the analysis of fungal ITS sequences, we PCR amplified this genomic region

using specific ITS primers,⁸ using the conditions described by Pinar et al.⁹ To identify the fungi, we compared the obtained sequence material to fungi ITS sequences available in the online public database NCBI, using the BLAST search program.¹⁰

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Observations on the results of water activity (aw) analysis

Water activity analysis is a widely-used technique in food storage control.¹¹ Its application in the field of cultural heritage conservation, on mummified biological samples, is innovative and pioneering.

The importance of relative humidity (RH) to conservation is immense,¹² and closely linked to the concept of water activity (aw), the parameter proportional to the escaping tendency of the water molecules present in the tissues constituting the mummy. Water activity (aw) is calculated as the ratio of the partial vapour pressure of water in tissues (Pw) to that of pure water (Pw0) at the sample's surface temperature.¹³

After a certain time, any substance placed in a sealed

Fig. 3: Direct microbiological sampling on the surface of mummy Cat. 2245. Picture by Marco Samadelli/Eurac Research, Institute for Mummy Studies.

Fig. 4: Sampling of spores present in the air inside display cases (Suppl. 19691). Picture by Marco Samadelli/Eurac Research, Institute for Mummy Studies.

Fig. 5: Positioning of the results of water activity (a_w) testing on the mummies in relation to the decay speed of organic tissues as a function of water activity (a_w) [Labuza, T.P., 1975].

environment reaches a “thermal and hygrometric” equilibrium with the air surrounding it. Accordingly, the substance’s moisture content reaches an equilibrium with the humidity of the environment (EMC). Under these conditions, the value of the air’s equilibrium relative humidity (ERH) corresponds to the water activity (a_w) value of the substance.¹⁴

From the chemical point of view, tissues constituting mummies can be considered as concentrated “solutions”, and measurement and limitation of water activity (a_w) are essential to the conservation process because they influence the life of microorganisms and enzyme activity. The greater the water activity (a_w) value, the faster the decay of organic tissue, as synthetically represented in the chart (Fig. 5).¹⁵

Relative humidity values higher than 65 %, combined with temperature values higher than 20 °C, promote the development of moulds and accelerate the metabolism of many harmful insects. It is scientifically demonstrated that, with water activity (a_w) lower than 0.3, it is possible to inhibit the majority of the causes of biochemical decay in organic tissue.¹⁶

A total of 106 mummified samples were subjected to water activity (a_w) tests. The results of the analysis are illustrated in Tables 1A and 1B (Tab. 1A and Tab. 1B).

The results of our water activity (a_w) examination shows that most of the analysed mummies are in the

range between 0.4 and 0.5 (a_w) (Fig. 6). No differences were noted, with respect to this type of analysis, between one mummy and the other, even when kept in different environments. This uniformity of results is not surprising, because the same homogeneity was observed in the climatic parameters of the museum’s exhibition environments and display cases, and of the mummy storage room.

In conclusion, observing the results of the water activity (a_w) analysis on the mummified samples, reported in tables 1A and 1B (Tab. 1A and Tab. 1B), and comparing them with recent theoretical and experimental studies relative to the conservation of organic mummified finds,¹⁷ it can be stated that:

1. the observed water activity levels are consistent with those expectable in the environmental climatic conditions provided by the museum,
2. the analysed mummies are preserved within the safety parameters provided for proper conservation, as they all remain within the ideal range between 0.25 – 0.65 (a_w), as shown in Fig. 5.¹⁸

4.2 Microbiological analysis

Through the fungal survey applied in this study, we were able to detect and identify different fungal genera and species on skin and textile samples taken from mummies from both the storage rooms and the display cases (Fig. 7). Interestingly, the number of

Mummy (INV. N.)	Museum location	Sampling date	Microbial survey		AW	Taw (°C)
			MEA2%	DG18		
Cat. 2211/2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 3	28/03/2017	FS46	FS45	0,4460	22,81
Cat. 2213/ 2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 009	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4580	22,53
Cat. 2215/2	Sala 11 vetrina 03	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4391	23,18
Cat. 2218/2	Sala 11 vetrina 03	03/04/2017	FS95	FS96	0,4530	23,09
Cat. 2220/ 3	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 09 - ripiano 1	31/03/2017	FS80	FS79	0,4476	22,40
Cat. 2223	Ex-Antichità - cassa	05/04/2017	-	-	0,4170	24,65
Cat. 2230/1	Sala 13 vetrina 01	05/04/2017	-	-	0,4920	24,58
Cat. 2231/02	Sala 11 vetrina 03	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4530	22,77
Cat. 2233	Ex-Antichità - cassa	05/04/2017	-	-	0,4239	24,31
Cat. 2245	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 1	29/03/2017	-	-	0,4290	21,70
Cat. 2253	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 1	28/03/2017	FS35	FS36	0,4221	22,32
Cat. 2254	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 3	28/03/2017	-	-	0,4339	22,44
Cat. 2256	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 1	28/03/2017	FS39	FS40	0,4021	22,49
Provv. 0549	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 2	28/03/2017	FS44	FS43	0,4540	22,75
Provv. 0578	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 4	29/03/2017	-	-	0,4200	21,48
Provv. 0610	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa + scaffale 14 - ripiano 1	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4460	22,10
Provv. 0611	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 07 - ripiano 2	29/03/2017	FS57	FS58	0,4891	25,15
Provv. 0612	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 07 - ripiano 1	30/03/2017	FS70	FS69	0,4605	22,33
Provv. 0731	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 09 - ripiano 2	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4310	22,62
Provv. 0996	Sala 12 vetrina 06	27/03/2017	FS21	FS22	0,4060	22,07
Provv. 1448	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 4	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4231	20,81
Provv. 1449	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 2	29/03/2017	FS53	FS54	0,4620	22,75
Provv. 1453	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 1	29/03/2017	-	-	0,5005	22,87
Provv. 1456	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 3	28/03/2017	FS48	FS47	0,4102	22,77
Provv. 1457	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 4	29/03/2017	-	-	0,4411	20,40
Provv. 1468	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 1	29/03/2017	FS55	FS56	0,5512	24,42
Provv. 1470/ 1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 05 - ripiano 4	27/03/2017	-	-	0,4150	20,65
Provv. 1471	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 07 - ripiano 3	29/03/2017	-	-	0,4722	25,56
Provv. 1473	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 007	30/03/2017	FS68	FS67	0,4485	21,82
Provv. 1475	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 3	28/03/2017	FS25	FS26	0,4489	20,63
Provv. 1478	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 09 - ripiano 2	30/03/2017	FS74	FS73	0,4591	22,75
Provv. 1480	Sala papiroteca - scaffale 12	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4611	21,06
Provv. 1488/1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 11 - scatola 06	05/04/2017	-	-	0,6185	22,44
Provv. 1513/1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 2	28/03/2017	-	-	0,4310	20,03
Provv. 4156/2	Magazzino legni, scatola 021	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4520	22,83
Provv. 4243/1	Magazzino legni, scatola 080	01/04/2017	-	-	0,4762	22,35
Provv. 4765/2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 4	06/04/2017	-	-	0,5170	22,55
Provv. 5532	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 10	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4611	20,62
Provv. 5535	Magazzino "legni "sabauda" scaffale Q 4	05/04/2017	-	-	0,5216	23,28
Provv. 6107	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 14 - ripiano 2	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4591	22,62
Provv. 6108	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 763	05/04/2017	-	-	0,5152	23,14
Provv. 6112	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 759	05/04/2017	-	-	0,5280	22,94
Provv. 6126/7	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 4 - ripiano 3	06/04/2017	-	-	0,5561	22,92
Provv. 8135	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 09 - ripiano 4	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4408	22,64
Suppl. 00278	Sala 15 vetrina 02	27/03/2017	-	-	0,4403	21,83
Suppl. 00293	Sala 02 vetrina 01	06/04/2017	FS103	FS104	0,4997	21,93
Suppl. 00304	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 3	29/03/2017	-	-	0,5662	23,88
Suppl. 05050	Sala 10 vetrina	27/03/2017	FS15	FS16	0,4431	21,92
Suppl. 05066	Sala 10 vetrina	27/03/2017	FS12	FS11	0,4540	21,77
Suppl. 05109	Magazzino "biblioteca", armadio A, ripiano 9	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4490	22,56
Suppl. 05142/2	Magazzino "biblioteca", armadio A, ripiano 9	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4231	22,21
Suppl. 05147	Magazzino "biblioteca", armadio A, ripiano 9	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4110	21,76
Suppl. 05154	Magazzino restauro	01/04/2017	-	-	0,5029	22,54
Suppl. 05226/2	Sala 08 vetrina 09	27/03/2017	-	-	0,3791	21,70
Suppl. 05227/2	Sala 08 vetrina 08	27/03/2017	FS14	FS13	0,4231	21,74
Suppl. 05270	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 2	28/03/2017	FS41	FS42	0,4131	22,58
Suppl. 05271	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 01 - ripiano 3	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4681	23,09
Suppl. 07715/01	Sala 08	05/04/2017	-	-	0,4745	22,91
Suppl. 07716	Sala 06 vetrina 07	05/04/2017	-	-	0,4906	23,56
Suppl. 07717	Soppalco - armadio 03 fibre vegetali - ripiano 3	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4673	22,77
Suppl. 07718	Magazzino legni, scatola 120	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4721	22,89
Suppl. 07719	Magazzino legni, scatola 117	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4511	22,87

Tab. 1A: The results of the water activity (aw) value for the mummies, correlated with the acquisition temperature value Taw (°C) of the room where the research operations were carried out.

Mummy (INV. N.)	Museum location	Sampling date	Microbial survey		AW	Taw (°C)
			MEA2%	DG18		
Suppl. 08876/a	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 1	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4460	22,63
Suppl. 08942	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 13 - ripiano 4	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4425	22,55
Suppl. 08943	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 05 - ripiano 4	27/03/2017	-	-	0,4328	20,89
Suppl. 08983/1	Magazzino legni, scatola 025	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4320	22,55
Suppl. 10534/3	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 05 - ripiano 3	27/03/2017	-	-	0,4100	21,37
Suppl. 11110	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 04 - ripiano 4	28/03/2017	-	-	0,4550	22,70
Suppl. 13086 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 759	05/04/2017	-	-	0,5410	22,46
Suppl. 13088	Sala 03 vetrina 05 IN	05/04/2017	-	-	0,5080	22,87
Suppl. 13966/1	Sala 03 vetrina 02 TdI	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4231	22,93
Suppl. 14061/2	Sala 02 vetrina 13	06/04/2017	-	-	0,4980	22,93
Suppl. 14064/2 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 008	01/04/2017	-	-	0,4690	21,71
Suppl. 14067, ex Suppl. 15815	Sala 02 vetrina 08	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4583	22,05
Suppl. 14168/01	Magazzino vasi giallo, stanza 02, armadio 8, TOP	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4561	22,75
Suppl. 14378/a	Sala 04 vetrina 07 (dentro sarcofago 14378)	03/04/2017	-	-	0,3951	23,21
Suppl. 14381/1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 3	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4490	22,87
Suppl. 14385/1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 3	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4330	21,16
Suppl. 14391/2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 3	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4450	22,66
Suppl. 14393/2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 3	28/03/2017	FS32	FS31	0,4310	22,05
Suppl. 14396/a	Sala 02 vetrina 16	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4591	22,86
Suppl. 14415/2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 2	29/03/2017	-	-	0,4404	22,36
Suppl. 14426/2	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 4	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4580	22,84
Suppl. 14435 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 005	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4391	22,95
Suppl. 14508	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 1	28/03/2017	FS30	FS29	0,4552	21,49
Suppl. 14533/1 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 4	28/03/2017	-	-	0,4340	22,31
Suppl. 14650	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 10	01/04/2017	-	-	0,4864	22,46
Suppl. 15741/1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 07 - ripiano 4	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4729	22,59
Suppl. 158 [...] = Suppl. 11173	Magazzino vasi rosso, stanza 02, scaffale 06	05/04/2017	-	-	0,5093	24,90
Suppl. 15809	Magazzino vasi giallo, Stanza 02, armadio 8, TOP	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4760	22,94
Suppl. 16090/2 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 14 - ripiano 2	06/04/2017	-	-	0,5260	22,58
Suppl. 16742	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 1	31/03/2017	-	-	0,4439	22,69
Suppl. 16743 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 06 - ripiano 2	28/03/2017	FS27	FS28	0,4710	21,04
Suppl. 16744 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 05 - ripiano 2	27/03/2017	FS06	FS05	0,4498	21,24
Suppl. 16747/1	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 05 - ripiano 2	30/03/2017	-	-	0,4751	22,49
Suppl. 16760 (?)	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 08 - ripiano 4	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4300	21,22
Suppl. 16770/2	Sala 02 vetrina 08 o ML sc 10	05/04/2017	-	-	0,4989	22,96
Suppl. 16771	Magazzino legni, scatola 011	01/04/2017	-	-	0,4080	22,14
Suppl. 16772/2	Magazzino legni, scatola 012	01/04/2017	-	-	0,4832	22,28
Suppl. 16773/2	Magazzino legni, scatola 013	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4484	22,98
Suppl. 16774	Magazzino legni, scatola 014	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4730	22,25
Suppl. 17045	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - scaffale 03 - ripiano 4	04/04/2017	-	-	0,4561	22,62
Suppl. 19691/3	Sala 12 vetrina 06	27/03/2017	-	-	0,4000	21,94
Suppl. 5288 Prov_575	Ipogeo - magazzino visitabile - cassa 760	06/07/2017	-	-	0,4870	22,17
Suppl. 8431	Sala 07 vetrina 04	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4458	24,68
Suppl. 8471	Sala 07 vetrina 06	03/04/2017	-	-	0,4439	24,26

Tab. 1B: Results of the water activity (aw) value for the mummies, correlated with the acquisition temperature value Taw (°C) of the room where the research operations were carried out.

Fig. 6: Relationship between the number of mummies and the results of the water activity (aw) analysis.

Fig. 7: Fungi detected on textiles and soft tissues of mummies from the storage room (Ipogeo, magazzino visitabile) and from display cases. The pictures on the upper right show a contact plate sampling on a grass mat and the fungal growth on the agar plate after incubation. The fungi marked with an asterisk have been detected both on the contact plates and in the air sampling.

different fungi detected on the storage room material (n=17) is substantially higher than the ones from the display cases (n=3). In addition, in contrast to the storage room samples, approximately half of the contact plates taken from the exhibition room samples display no fungal growth at all. This result indicates that the exhibition room material has a lower fungal spore and mycelia load in comparison to the material from the storage room. Further comparison of the detected contact plate fungi with the results obtained from air sampling indicates the presence of air-borne fungi in all the material analysed (Fig. 7,

asterisks). For example, fungal species belonging to the genus *Penicillium spp.* were detected both on the material and in the air in the display cases. However, beside this acquisition and exchange of airborne fungal spores and mycelia, there still appear to be indigenous fungal communities present on different material. The fungal communities detected on the storage room textile or soft-tissue material on display clear sample-specific differences (Fig. 7). These differences become even more apparent when we take a closer look at the functional properties of the “material-specific” fungal species detected. Fungi

such as *Bjerkandera adusta*, *Aspergillus tubingensis*, *Cladosporium cladosporioides* and *Cytospora sacculus* were only detected on the textile/plant material.¹⁹ For example, while sampling a grass mat using contact plates, we only observed the presence of one fungus, *Aspergillus welwitschiae*, which is known to be involved in the breakdown of fibrous plant material such as sisal²⁰ (Fig. 7). Taken together, almost all the fungi detected in the textile material are commonly found saprophytes involved in degrading plant remains. In contrast, the soft tissue harboured unique fungal species such as *Alternaria infectoria*, a saprophytic fungus known to thrive on skin tissue.²¹ In addition, we detected several *Penicillium* species (e.g. *Penicillium chrysogenum*) on the soft tissues, known for their proteolytic potential.²² There is therefore a clear indication of the presence of material-specific fungal communities.

5. Final considerations

In sum, our results indicate a still present biodegradational potential in the form of tissue-specific fungal communities (spores and mycelia), which could

become a biodegradative risk as soon as the environmental conditions change, for example, at water activity levels above 0.65 (aw), which promote fungal growth.²³ It is therefore of the utmost importance to keep the water activity levels of these unique cultural assets under constant control.

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Notes

¹ Scattolin Morecroft, in *JEA* 92 (2006), pp. 278, 281.

² Moiso, *La storia del Museo Egizio* (2016).

³ For an overview on the mummies from Donati's and Drovetti's collection, see Fiore Marochetti in Boano and Rabino Massa (eds.), *Mummie Egizie in Piemonte* (2012), pp. 5–6; Boano et al., *Mummie e mummificazione* (2015); Delorenzi, Grilletto, *Le mummie del Museo Egizio di Torino* (1989).

⁴ Boano et al., *Le mummie del Museo Egizio di Torino* (2008); Marro, *Scavi Italiani in Egitto* (1930).

⁵ Boano et al. in Boano and Rabino Massa (eds.), *Mummie Egizie in Piemonte* (2012), p. 21.

⁶ Piñar et al., *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 86/2 (2013); Piñar et al., *Extremophiles* 18/4 (2014).

⁷ Michaelsen et al., *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation* 58/3 (2006).

⁸ White et al., in Innis et al. (eds.), *PCR Protocols: A Guide to Methods and Applications* (1990).

⁹ Piñar et al., *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 86/2 (2013).

¹⁰ Altschul et al., *Nucleic Acids Research* 25/17 (1997).

¹¹ Cheftel et al. (eds.), *Biochimica e tecnologia degli alimenti* (1999).

¹² FprEN 16242.

¹³ EN 15803.

¹⁴ EN 15803.

¹⁵ Labuza, in Cho-Kyun Rha (ed.), *Theory, Determination and Control*, 1975.

¹⁶ Labuza, in Cho-Kyun Rha (ed.), *Theory, Determination*

and Control, 1975; Shin, *Oxygen-Free Museum Cases*, 1998; Samadelli et al., *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 14/6 (2013).

¹⁷ Samadelli et al., *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 14/6 (2013).

¹⁸ Labuza, in Cho-Kyun Rha (ed.), *Theory, Determination and Control*, 1975.

¹⁹ Bensch et al., *Studies in Mycology* 67 (2010); Fan et al., *Fungal Biology* 119/5 (2015); Perrone et al., *Applied Environmental Microbiology* 72/1 (2006); Wang et al., *Canadian Journal of Microbiology* 49/11 (2003).

²⁰ Duarte et al., *Frontiers in Microbiology* 9 (2018).

²¹ Dubois et al., *Mycopathologia* 160 (2005).

²² Martín et al., *Meat Science* 62 (2002).

²³ Labuza, in Cho-Kyun Rha (ed.), *Theory, Determination and Control* (1975).

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